

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D9.5

Static Hazard Maps (alpha version)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANP	Analytical Network Process
BSA	Bivariate Statistical Analysis
CR	Consistency Ratio
DL	Deep Learning
EO	Eart Observation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GSI	Geological Strength Index
IoT	Internet of Things

MCDM	Multicriteria Decision Making
ML	Machine Learning
RMR	Rock Mass Rating
RS	Remote Sensing
SMR	Slope Mass Rating
UAVs	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TERRAVISION project is focused on enhancing sustainability and operational efficiency within the mining sector through the integration of advanced Earth Observation (EO) technologies. It aims to develop a comprehensive platform that merges satellite, airborne, and ground-based remote sensing data, supporting the full raw materials value chain—from exploration to post-closure monitoring. Key objectives include the modernization of exploration practices, improved risk and hazard management, optimization of resource extraction, and assurance of environmental compliance. The Dynamic Hazard Map service leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning, Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, and remote sensing to assess and forecast ground stability risks in mining environments, supporting early warning and informed decision-making.

This report presents the outcomes of the initial phase in the development of the Dynamic Hazard Map, specifically the creation of its static component. This foundational stage is critical, as it provides the essential spatial and geotechnical datasets upon which the dynamic elements will be constructed in subsequent phases of the project. The Alpha Version delivers a static hazard map for the TernaMag mine site, developed through drone surveys, geological, geotechnical and structural mapping, and multi-criteria analysis combining statistical and expert weighting of factors like slope, lithology, and rock quality. Future phases aim to evolve this into a dynamic system by incorporating real-time monitoring data and advanced modeling to improve hazard prediction and responsiveness.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this work is the development of the Alpha Version of the Dynamic Hazard Map service, with an exclusive focus on the TernaMag mine site in Greece. This initial phase aimed to compile and analyze geological, geotechnical, structural, and topographical data to produce a comprehensive Static Hazard Map that will serve as the foundation for the system's future dynamic capabilities. The process included high-resolution drone surveys, lithological and structural mapping, and geotechnical classification using the Geological Strength Index (GSI) system. Visible landslide occurrences were mapped and categorized by type and lithological domain, contributing to the identification of dominant failure mechanisms on site.

To quantify the influence of key controlling parameters—namely slope angle, lithology, rock mass quality, and structural density—the analysis employed both bivariate statistical methods and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). These evaluations provided weighted inputs that reflect the relative contribution of each factor to slope instability, supporting the generation of hazard zones across the mine area. The resulting Static Hazard Map not only consolidates critical site information but also sets a robust foundation for integrating real-time monitoring and advanced predictive modeling in subsequent phases. Although preliminary preparations have also been made for the Tharsis and Canteras sites, the current work targets TernaMag due to data readiness and project prioritization at this stage.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodological framework applied for the development of the Alpha Version of the Dynamic Hazard Map, focused on the TernaMag mine site in Greece. The approach followed a

stepwise workflow beginning with high-resolution drone-based data acquisition, which generated a dense 3D point cloud used for detailed structural and surface analysis. From this dataset, essential thematic layers were developed—including lithology, slope, rock mass quality (via the Geological Strength Index), and structural density. These layers supported the mapping and classification of visible landslides and the characterization of failure mechanisms in accordance with established geological and geotechnical standards.

To assess landslide susceptibility, a combination of bivariate statistical analysis and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was employed to assign weights to the controlling parameters. These weighted layers were integrated using GIS tools to produce a composite hazard index and the resulting Static Hazard Map for TernaMag. This output forms the core deliverable of the Alpha Version and a foundational reference for the transition toward a fully dynamic hazard assessment system in later project phases.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The Dynamic Hazard Map service in TERRAVISION project intends to advance landslide hazard assessment in mining environments by developing an innovative dynamic hazard map for early warning and decision making in the mines applied. This foundational work integrates high-resolution spatial data, geological and geotechnical analyses, and both statistical and expert-driven methodologies to identify and weight critical factors influencing slope stability. The insights gained highlight the dominant role of slope angle and lithology in landslide susceptibility and lay the groundwork for a dynamic, near real-time hazard monitoring system.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- An Alpha Version static hazard map has been developed for the TernaMag mine, laying the groundwork for a fully dynamic hazard assessment system tailored to mining environments.
- High-resolution drone surveys, geological, structural mapping, and geotechnical classification provided detailed spatial data essential for assessing slope stability.
- Statistical analysis (BSA) and expert judgment (AHP) were used to weight controlling parameters.
- The static hazard map delineates five hazard classes, enabling clear spatial understanding of landslide risk zones within the mine.
- Next development stages will integrate dynamic, real-time data to enable continuous slope stability monitoring.
- More detailed geotechnical classifications (e.g., RMR and SMR) will complement existing GSI-based assessments.
- Machine learning models trained on historical and real-time data will improve predictive accuracy, with robust validation planned.

1. Introduction

The field of dynamic landslide hazard mapping is undergoing rapid progress, with numerous studies employing machine learning, Remote Sensing (RS), and data-driven methodologies to enhance landslide prediction and risk assessment (Ersayin et al., 2025; Bijing et al., 2023; Ataollah et al., 2018; Yan et al., 2024, Al-Najjar et al., 2021, Tengtrairatet al., 2021). While these advancements have significantly contributed to our understanding of natural slope behavior, the Dynamic Hazard map of TERRAVISION project distinguishes itself by applying these techniques within the uniquely dynamic context of mining environments. In contrast to natural slopes, where several parameters like geological and topographic conditions are relatively stable, mines are continuously evolving systems. Excavation activities regularly alter terrain geometry, lithological exposure, and geotechnical conditions. This variability introduces complexity but also presents an opportunity to deliver more adaptive and responsive hazard assessment tools. The added value of the Dynamic Hazard Map lies in its capacity to capture and respond to these constant changes, positioning it at the forefront of innovation in geohazard management.

Building upon this need for adaptability, the Dynamic Hazard Map service is conceived as a state-of-the-art Industry 4.0 platform aimed at enhancing early warning capabilities and enabling informed decision-making in mining environments. By integrating multi-source datasets, including satellite imagery, ground-based sensors, and historical landslide records, the system dynamically assesses the probability of slope failure in both spatial and temporal dimensions, translating this data into actionable risk intelligence.

This service leverages the synergistic application of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Remote Sensing (RS), and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies to continuously update risk assessments and adjust alarm thresholds in response to evolving site conditions. In scenarios where historical datasets are sparse or incomplete, numerical back-analysis modelling is employed to supplement the predictive framework. The system incorporates real-time field measurements, satellite monitoring inputs, and advanced predictive models, all accessible through a user-centric decision support interface. Furthermore, Machine Learning techniques are applied to filter erroneous sensor data, enhancing the robustness and reliability of the hazard evaluations.

The primary objective of the project is to develop and operationalise the Dynamic Hazard Map service, capable of delivering near real-time hazard assessments and forecasts for mining sites and their surrounding areas. Core activities include:

- Defining the relevant data types for inclusion in hazard mapping, considering the temporal and spatial resolution as well as the distribution characteristics of deployed sensors.
- Developing machine learning algorithms to mitigate noise and inaccuracies in sensor datasets.
- Constructing preliminary geotechnical models to identify static controlling parameters that influence hazard index calculations.
- Investigating the role of dynamic factors—such as precipitation, seismic events, and blasting vibrations—as either preparatory or triggering influences in slope or ground instabilities.
- Applying Multicriteria Decision Making (MCDM) methodologies, including the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Analytical Network Process (ANP), to assign weights reflecting the relative importance of various hazard-controlling parameters.

- Deploying the Dynamic Hazard Map within a web-based Geographic Information System (GIS) platform to ensure seamless accessibility for mining personnel across diverse device types, including desktops, tablets, and mobile phones.

This integrated approach not only addresses current limitations in geohazard forecasting but also sets the foundation for a more resilient, proactive risk management strategy tailored to the complex realities of modern mining operations.

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable presents the Alpha Version of the Static Hazard Map for the TernaMag mine site, detailing the methodology, data acquisition, and analytical processes used to assess slope stability. It lays the groundwork for the future integration of dynamic, real-time monitoring capabilities within the TERRAVISION project.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an initial, comprehensive assessment of landslide hazards at the TernaMag mine site through the creation of a static hazard map. This serves as a critical first step in establishing a dynamic hazard monitoring framework that incorporates real-time data and advanced modelling techniques, ultimately aiming to improve safety and risk management in mining operations.

1.3 Intended Audience

This report is classified as Public and is primarily intended for all project partners, with particular emphasis on the leaders of tasks associated with WP7-8 Analysis Ready Data and Raw Spectral Signatures, WP9-10 EO Services for the Mining Industry, and the WP11 Green & Resilience Accountability component. The aim of the deliverable is to develop and present a foundational static landslide hazard map for the TernaMag mine site that integrates geological, geotechnical, and structural data as a basis for creating a dynamic, real-time hazard monitoring system tailored to mining environments.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

The sections following the Introduction provide a detailed account of the methodology applied for the compilation of the Static Hazard Map (Alpha Version), along with the corresponding analysis results. Additionally, the final section of the report outlines the next steps and anticipated enhancements that will inform the development of the final Dynamic Hazard Map deliverable.

This deliverable is intrinsically connected to multiple work packages within the TERRAVISION project. It represents a pivotal contribution to WP9 and WP10, which are dedicated to the development of Earth Observation (EO) services specifically tailored to support the end-to-end lifecycle of critical raw and secondary materials in the mining sector.

Moreover, the successful implementation of this deliverable is strongly dependent on the services delivered through WP4 focused on the Requirements, Specifications and Overall Architecture of the

project, as well as WP7, and WP8 focused on Analysis Ready Data and Raw Spectral Signatures. These work packages play a critical role in ensuring the readiness, quality, and continuous availability of essential datasets, particularly those derived from in situ sensor networks. Their contributions are fundamental for supporting the integration of real-time and near-real-time monitoring data, which are vital for the transition from static to fully dynamic hazard assessment and for enhancing the overall accuracy and responsiveness of the system.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology applied in the development of the Alpha Version product for Work Package 9.5 (WP9.5), the Dynamic Hazard Map. The purpose is to describe the approach, processes, and tools implemented during the initial phase of the map's creation. As previously noted, the current version consists of a static hazard map specifically produced for the TernaMag mine site in Greece. Extensive preparatory work has also been carried out for the Canteras and Tharsis mine sites; however, in this Alpha Version, only the TernaMag site is represented with a completed static hazard map. This output serves as a foundational component for the future development of a fully dynamic hazard mapping system, with the methodology presented here forming the basis for subsequent enhancements.

2.1 Stepwise Approach

The methodological framework adopted for the development of the static hazard map at the TernaMag site was designed to integrate high-resolution spatial data with geological and geotechnical analysis. The workflow comprised several distinct yet interconnected stages, progressing from data acquisition to hazard zonation. Each stage is outlined below.

2.1.1. Drone-Based Data Acquisition

The initial stage involved the execution of drone flights over the TernaMag site to acquire high-resolution aerial imagery. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) equipped with advanced cameras, enabled the capture of detailed topographic and surface condition data. The surveys covered the main areas of geotechnical interest and were planned to ensure sufficient overlap and ground control for accurate georeferencing.

2.1.2. Generation of High-Resolution Point Cloud

The collected aerial imagery was processed using photogrammetric techniques to produce a dense and accurate point cloud. This three-dimensional dataset provided a detailed representation of the site's terrain and surface features, forming the spatial foundation for all subsequent analyses. The point cloud also facilitated the extraction of structural and morphological information critical for hazard assessment.

2.1.3. Lithological Mapping

A simplified lithological map was developed based on visual interpretation of the point cloud, supported by existing geological knowledge of the area. Surface expressions of different rock types were delineated, allowing the site to be divided into lithological domains. This mapping served as a fundamental input for further analysis. Lithology is a critical component because different rock types have varying strengths, weathering characteristics, and permeability, all of which directly affect slope stability. Identifying these variations helps in assessing which areas are more susceptible to landslides and in understanding the mechanisms that may trigger slope failure. Therefore, accurate lithological delineation improves the reliability of the static hazard map.

2.1.4. Structural Mapping: Joints and Faults

Structural features such as joints, fractures, and faults were identified and systematically mapped using the high-resolution 3D surface model. The mapped discontinuities were classified by type and grouped into distinct joint sets based on their orientation. This structural mapping provided critical input for the hazard assessment, as the spatial distribution and configuration of these sets are key factors influencing slope stability and potential failure mechanisms.

2.1.5. GSI Classification

The Geological Strength Index (GSI), as proposed by Marinos et al. (2000), was utilized to assess the rock mass quality across the TernaMag site. GSI was selected for this phase due to the absence of sufficient geotechnical data required for applying more comprehensive classification systems such as the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) developed by Bieniawski (1973) or the Slope Mass Rating (SMR) developed by Romana (1993), which incorporate additional structural and geomechanical parameters along with the slope characteristics. The classification was carried out through visual interpretation of lithology, structural characteristics, and discontinuity conditions, as derived from high-resolution point cloud data and drone imagery. Despite its qualitative nature, the GSI index served as a valuable tool for characterizing the rock mass and supporting the evaluation of slope stability and failure susceptibility in the current stage of the project.

2.1.6. Landslide Mapping and Classification

Visible evidence of landslides and localized instabilities was mapped and classified according to the type of failure (e.g., planar, rotational), following the characterization framework proposed by Varnes (1978), and the corresponding lithological domain involved in each case. This classification provided valuable insight into the relationship between geological conditions and observed failure mechanisms, serving as a foundational input for the subsequent statistical evaluation and hazard mapping processes.

2.1.7. Development of Thematic Layers

A series of thematic layers representing key event-controlling parameters were generated using GIS techniques (Ayalew et al., 2003, 2004, 2005). These layers included slope angle, lithology, discontinuity density, GSI classification, and proximity to structural features. To ensure consistency and facilitate their integration in multi-criteria analyses, all layers were standardized in terms of format, resolution, and spatial extent.

2.1.8. Bivariate Statistical Analysis

A bivariate statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationship between observed landslide occurrences and the relevant controlling parameters (Suzen et al., 2004). This approach enabled the quantification of each parameter's influence on slope failure by assessing its spatial correlation with the distribution of mapped landslides. The analysis provided weights for each parameter category based on the statistical frequency of landslides occurring within each category.

2.1.9. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

In parallel with the statistical analysis, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1980, 2000, 2003) was applied to incorporate expert judgment in the evaluation of controlling parameters. A structured comparison of parameter importance was conducted, and consistency ratios were used to validate the results. This process enabled a more balanced and transparent weight assignment that combined both data-driven and expert-informed perspectives.

2.1.10. Weight Assignment and Integration of Layers

The weights derived from the AHP, and statistical analysis were applied to the corresponding thematic layers. These weighted layers were then integrated to produce a composite hazard index. The result was a spatial model representing relative landslide susceptibility across the TernaMag site.

2.1.11. Compilation of the Static Hazard Map

Finally, the integrated hazard index was visualized as a static hazard map, delineating zones of varying susceptibility to slope failure. The map, compiled in a GIS environment (Ayalew et al., 2003, 2004, 2005), provides a spatial overview of potential geohazard-prone areas and serves as the Alpha Version output for WP9.5. It will act as a foundational element for future enhancements involving dynamic, real-time data integration and automated updates.

2.2 Data Used

At this stage, the data utilised for the development of the Static Hazard Map derive exclusively from drone-based surveys carried out at the TernaMag mine site. These surveys generated a high-resolution 3D point cloud, which served as the foundational dataset for subsequent geological and geotechnical analyses. The exceptional level of detail provided by the point cloud enabled the systematic identification and mapping of visible discontinuities, including joints, fractures, and major faults. This structural mapping formed a critical input for understanding the geotechnical conditions affecting slope stability.

Complementing the structural analysis, the Geological Strength Index (GSI) classification system was applied to assess the quality and mechanical behaviour of the rock mass. The GSI, a widely used geotechnical tool, offers a semi-quantitative evaluation of rock mass conditions based on the visual characteristics of lithology, structural features, and the surface condition of discontinuities (Marinos et al, 2000).

In parallel, a simplified lithological mapping was performed using visual interpretation of the point cloud and existing geological knowledge of the area. Although not detailed at this stage, this lithological framework provided necessary geological context, supporting the correlation between material types and observed or potential instability mechanisms. Together, these datasets formed the basis for generating thematic layers used in the subsequent hazard analysis and map development.

3. Results / Current Progress

This chapter presents the results, which are organised into three distinct stages. The first stage involves the creation of various thematic layers representing geological, structural, and geotechnical information. The second stage covers the application of two statistical methods—Bivariate Statistical Analysis and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)—along with the presentation of their results. Finally, the third stage focuses on the compilation of the static hazard map based on the integrated analysis.

3.1 Spatial Analysis and Thematic Mapping

At this stage of development for the Alpha Version, several thematic maps have been produced, as outlined in the methodology. These maps compile and visualize layers of information related to the topography, geological and structural features, as well as geotechnical properties of the TernaMag mine site.

The topography as shown in Figure 1 is characterised by a stepped bench configuration with steep inter-bench slopes, typical of open pit excavation. Slope angles between benches commonly reach values of approximately 70 degrees, indicating a relatively aggressive pit design. This steep geometry, in combination with the underlying geological and structural conditions, has important implications for the stability of the exposed rock faces.

Figure 1 Slope angle map showing inter-bench slope gradients in degrees. The steepest slopes shown with the lighter shades of gray while the roads of the open pit and the gentlest slopes shown with the darkest gray shades.

Regarding the geological setting, two major lithological domains are observed, distinguishing the upper levels of the open pit from the lower sections. As illustrated in Figure 2 below, the upper part is dominated by a sedimentary formation, whereas at depth, transitions to a metamorphic unit that also hosts the ore-bearing veins.

Figure 2 Base lithological map of the TernaMag open pit showing the two main lithological units, the metamorphic bedrock which hosts the ore lenses in green and the sedimentary upper formation in orange.

Regarding the structural setting of the site, three dominant joint sets can be identified, along with a few larger faults, as illustrated in Figure 3. The intersection of these discontinuities results in a blocky rock mass structure, which is also reflected in the GSI classification shown in the corresponding Figure 4. This structural configuration plays a significant role in the geomechanical behavior of the slope.

Figure 3 Structural map highlighting the major joint sets and faults at the site.

Figure 4 Geological Strength Index (GSI) classification of the rock mass.

At this stage, a comprehensive landslide mapping was conducted to identify and classify the various types of slope failures occurring within the mine. As illustrated in the Figure 5 below, the predominant landslide types include rotational and translational slides, rockfalls, wedge failures, and planar failures. Each failure type reflects specific geological and structural conditions, providing valuable insight into the mechanisms driving slope instability across the site.

Figure 5 Map of landslide types identified within the mine

Building on the structural mapping, two complementary analytical products were developed to deepen the understanding of the rock mass characteristics and the factors influencing failure mechanisms. These products, presented in the figures below, include a structural density heatmap Figure 7, which visualizes the concentration of fractures and joints across the site, and a structural intersection heatmap Figure 8, highlighting zones where multiple discontinuity sets intersect. Landslide locations are also indicated as points on both maps, providing valuable spatial correlation between structural features and observed slope failures. Together, these maps offer critical insights into potential zones of weakness and block formation within the rock mass.

Figure 6 Map showing the distribution of structures with points indicating locations of structural intersections.

Figure 7 Structural density heatmap showing the concentration of fractures and joints across the site.

Figure 8 Structural intersection heatmap highlighting zones where multiple discontinuity sets intersect.

3.2 Statistical Evaluation of Event Controlling Parameters

The following section presents the results of the statistical analyses conducted to evaluate the relative influence of various controlling parameters on slope instability. Two methods were applied: Bivariate Statistical Analysis and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), each providing complementary insights into the significance and weighting of the factors contributing to landslide susceptibility.

3.2.1 Bivariate statistical analysis

The Bivariate Statistical Analysis approach is based on evaluating landslide frequency in relation to each controlling parameter individually. For each parameter, the frequency of landslide occurrence within its defined categories is assessed, and weights are assigned accordingly. Categories with higher landslide frequencies are given higher weight values, reflecting their greater contribution to slope instability within the study area.

The following graphs illustrate the distribution of landslide occurrences across the different categories of each controlling parameter, which guided the assignment of weights. Starting with slope, Figure 9, a clear trend is observed—steeper slope angles are associated with a higher frequency of landslides. In terms of lithology, Figure 10, the majority of recorded landslides occur within the sedimentary formation, although a notable number is also present in the underlying metamorphic unit.

Additionally, the chart displaying landslide type frequency confirms that most failures are rotational or translational, which aligns with the observed geological and geotechnical conditions.

Figure 9 Slope and Landslide Frequency. More landslides occur in steeper slope categories.

Figure 10 Lithology and Landslide Frequency. Most landslides are found in the sedimentary formation.

Extending the analysis to geotechnical parameters, the GSI classification in Figure 11 shows that nearly all recorded landslides fall within the category of blocky to very blocky rock mass. This finding aligns with the results of the structural density parameter, Figure 12, where most landslides are located in areas classified as having low to very low structural density. This outcome suggests that, within the current context, areas with lower fracture density are not necessarily more stable. On the contrary, the concentration of landslides observed in zones with sparse structural features indicates that slope failures are likely governed by broader geomechanical conditions rather than by discrete structural controls. Specifically, factors such as low rock mass strength, poor coherence, and weak lithological composition appear to play a more critical role. This points to a failure mechanism in which the entire rock mass is compromised, rather than failures being primarily driven by individual joints or fault planes. Such behavior

highlights the importance of considering the combined influence of structural, lithological, and geotechnical properties when assessing slope stability.

Figure 11 GSI and Landslide Frequency. Landslides mainly fall within the blocky to very blocky rock mass category.

Figure 12 Structural Density and Landslide Frequency. Landslides mostly occur in areas with low structural density.

Figure 13 Landslide Type Frequency. Distribution of landslides by failure type, showing a predominance of rotational and translational slides.

Additionally, Figure 13, which presents the frequency of landslide types, confirms that the majority of failures are rotational or translational. This observation aligns closely with the prevailing geological and geotechnical conditions at the site. Synthesizing the findings from the Bivariate Statistical Analysis, it becomes evident that steep slope angles within the open pit represent the most influential factor in landslide occurrence. The dominance of rotational and translational failures reflects the geomechanical environment as defined by key parameters such as slope, lithology, GSI, and structural density.

Most recorded landslides are concentrated within the sedimentary formation, reinforcing the connection between lithology and failure behaviour. This formation is characterized by relatively low structural complexity, indicating that the observed instabilities are more likely governed by the mechanical properties of the rock mass itself rather than by clearly defined structural discontinuities. The data collectively suggest that in this setting, slope failures are predominantly lithologically driven, shaped by inherent material weaknesses and overall rock mass behaviour rather than specific structural controls.

All weights assigned to the categories of each parameter, based on the bivariate analysis, are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Assigned Weights for Each Parameter Category. Summary of weight values assigned to the categories of each controlling parameter based on bivariate statistical analysis.

Controlling parameters	Parameter categories	Landslide frequency	Weight (BSA)
Slope	Extremely steep	27%	2
	Very Steep	32%	3
	Steep	35%	4
	Gentle	3%	1
	Very Gentle	3%	1
Lithology	Metamorphic bedrock	38%	1
	Sedimentary formation	62%	2
GSI	20-30	5%	2
	25-35	5%	2
	30-40	5%	2
	35-45	16%	3
	40-50	32%	4
	45-55	16%	3
	50-60	16%	3
	55-65	3%	1
Structural density	Very high	5%	1
	High	5%	1
	Medium	5%	1
	Low	41%	2
	Very low	44%	3

3.2.2 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) Weighting

In this section, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is applied to further refine the weighting of the controlling parameters based on their relative importance in landslide occurrence. Unlike the bivariate analysis, which considers each parameter independently, AHP allows for pairwise comparisons and incorporates expert judgment to evaluate the influence of each factor. The resulting weights are used to construct the final static hazard map.

The pairwise comparison matrix shown in the Table 2 below reflects the relative importance of the four event-controlling parameters—slope angle, lithology, GSI classification, and structural density (joints)—as determined through expert judgment and supported by geological and geotechnical reasoning. Each cell in the matrix indicates how much more important one parameter is compared to another. For example, slope was judged to be three times more important than lithology and twice as important as both GSI and joints. Conversely, lithology was considered significantly less influential across all comparisons. The normalized weights (w) derived from the matrix indicate that slope carries the highest influence followed by GSI, joints and lithology. These weight values were used in the multi-criteria evaluation process to compile the final static hazard map. The consistency ratio (CR) for the matrix is **0.0167**, which is well below the commonly accepted threshold of 0.10, indicating a high level of consistency in the judgments and thus validating the reliability of the results.

Table 2 Pairwise comparison matrix and resulting weights for the four controlling parameters used in the AHP analysis.

Controlling parameters	Slope	Lithology	GSI	Structure density	Weight (AHP)
Slope	1	3	2	2	0.42
Lithology	1/3	1	1/3	1/2	0.11
GSI	1/2	3	1	2	0.29
Structures density	1/2	2	1/2	1	0.18
Consistency ratio (CR)					0.0167

3.3 COMPILATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE STATIC HAZARD MAP

As the concluding step of the analysis, the static hazard map was compiled by integrating the weighted thematic layers. We assigned weights to each controlling parameter according to the values derived from the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), while category-specific weights for each parameter were based on the results of the Bivariate Statistical Analysis (BSA). The composite hazard index generated from this weighted integration provides a spatial representation of landslide susceptibility across the TernaMag open pit mine. The resulting static hazard map, presented in the Figure 14 below, delineates zones of varying hazard intensity within the mine’s extents. The hazard levels are categorized into five classes: very high, high, medium, low, and very low, facilitating clear identification of areas with different susceptibility to landslide occurrence.

Figure 14 Final static hazard map of the TernaMag open pit mine, illustrating landslide susceptibility.

4. Conclusions

The development of the Static Hazard Map for the TernaMag mine site marks a significant step toward establishing a comprehensive, dynamic ground stability monitoring and forecasting system tailored for mining environments. This Alpha Version has demonstrated the feasibility and value of integrating high-resolution drone surveys, geological and structural mapping, and geotechnical classification to assess slope stability and delineate hazard-prone zones. By applying both bivariate statistical analysis and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), the project has successfully evaluated the influence of key controlling parameters such as slope, lithology, rock mass quality, and structural density.

The results have revealed that slope angle is the dominant factor in landslide occurrence at the site, with most failures occurring within the sedimentary formation and manifesting as rotational or translational slides. The findings also highlighted that, in this particular setting, slope failures are more closely tied to lithological and geomechanical conditions rather than to structural complexity, suggesting that material properties play a more critical role than fracture density.

The completion of this phase lays the essential groundwork for the transition to the fully dynamic hazard map, which will incorporate real-time data from in situ sensors, satellite imagery, and environmental monitoring systems. This future phase aims to enable predictive modelling and timely decision support through the integration of Artificial Intelligence, Remote Sensing, and Internet of Things technologies.

Moreover, the approach developed in this Alpha Version will serve as the template for expanding hazard mapping services to the Tharsis and Canteras mine sites. Although these locations will follow the same methodology for creating static layers, the project will move directly to machine learning-based hazard modelling, streamlining the process and enabling scalable deployment across sites.

5. Next Steps

The completion of the Static Hazard Map for the TernaMag site represents a foundational milestone toward the development of the fully operational Dynamic Hazard Map. While the static phase has provided critical insights through the integration of geological, geotechnical, structural, and topographic data, the next phase aims to enhance hazard prediction capabilities by incorporating temporally and spatially dynamic information. In terms of geotechnical characterization, the current GSI-based rock mass classification will be expanded and refined through the use of more detailed indices, such as the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) and Slope Mass Rating (SMR) systems, which provide greater resolution in assessing rock quality and slope stability conditions.

The forthcoming stage will involve the integration of multiple real-time and near-real-time data sources to enable continuous monitoring and forecasting of slope stability. In addition to the static layers—such as lithology, slope geometry, rock mass quality, and structural characteristics—the dynamic component will include:

- **Weather forecasts**, particularly precipitation data, which will be incorporated as a potential triggering factor for ground instability.
- **Ground-based radar systems** installed to continuously monitor surface displacements on selected critical slopes.
- **Satellite imagery** to detect subtle surface deformations over time across the broader area of interest.
- **In situ sensors**, including inclinometers, extensimeters, tiltmeters, and piezometers, which will provide continuous measurements of deformation, displacement, and pore water pressure conditions within the rock mass.

These dynamic datasets will contribute to a real-time understanding of the evolving ground conditions, making the hazard assessment both temporally and spatially responsive.

In parallel, high-resolution historical satellite imagery is expected to be acquired. This data will support the validation and refinement of the existing landslide inventory by identifying previously undetected events and confirming past failures. Furthermore, back-analysis of these historical landslides will be conducted to better understand the failure mechanisms and the controlling parameters involved. These results will be incorporated into machine learning models. The models will be trained to recognize the precursory conditions and parameter combinations that have historically led to slope failures. Through this data-driven approach, the system will improve its predictive accuracy over time, adapting to the specific characteristics of each monitored site.

The convergence of static and dynamic inputs will enable the transition from a static hazard representation to a continuously evolving, intelligent decision-support system. The Dynamic Hazard Map will not only inform day-to-day operational safety in active mining areas but also support long-term risk management and planning by offering reliable early warning capabilities tailored to the highly variable and changing nature of mine environments.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the predictive models, a robust validation framework will be implemented. The available dataset will be divided, using 70% for training and 30% for validation of the machine learning models. Additionally, the intention is real-time measurements from in situ sensors to serve as an independent source of validation. This dual approach will allow for the cross-verification of model predictions with observed site behavior, strengthening confidence in the system's outputs and its ability to adapt to actual ground conditions.

A key challenge in achieving this dynamic capability is the availability of high-quality historical data, which is crucial for training accurate and robust machine learning models. The reliability of predictive outputs is highly dependent on the richness of input datasets, particularly those capturing past landslide events, deformation patterns, and ground response under varying environmental conditions. While satellite imagery and geological data offer some insights, certain dynamic parameters—such as displacement or pore pressure readings from inclinometers, extensimeters, and piezometers—lack historical records, as these instruments are being installed specifically for the needs of the TERRAVISION. This limited availability of time-series sensor data poses a challenge for early model development and reduces the opportunity for back-validation using long-term ground behavior trends. Addressing this constraint requires careful use of back-analysis techniques, synthetic data generation where appropriate, and the progressive improvement of model accuracy as more real-time data becomes available throughout the project's lifecycle.

For the additional sites of Tharsis and Canteras, the next steps will include the development of their respective static hazard layers following the same methodology used in TernaMag. These static layers will form the essential baseline for future dynamic hazard assessments at each site. However, no expert-based statistical analysis (such as Bivariate or AHP methods) will be performed for these locations. Instead, the project will transition directly to the machine learning-based approach that was described across all sites.

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